

**RECOMMENDATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN
CONSUMER PROTECTION AND ADVERTISING REGULATION IN
DIGITAL AREA.**

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#OnlineAdvertising #DigitalConsumerProtection #InternationalGuidelines

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Purpose of the study is to investigate how national legal standards can be developed and implemented to address the ethical, privacy, and human rights challenges posed by online advertising. This article examines the complex landscape of international recommendations for governing online advertising. The findings can enable developing national standards that offer better protection to consumers in the context of online advertising, ensuring transparency, safety, and trust in the digital marketplace, enabling everyone to participate fully in it. This study aims to contribute valuable insights into the regulation of online advertising and propose practical solutions for urgently needed legal upgrades and harmonization of legislation with the international standards related to digital advertising, given its exponential growth and absence of boundaries on the internet.

Online advertising has grown exponentially in recent years into almost \$600 billion industry, representing over 50% of total media advertising expenditure globally, according to PwC “Global Entertainment and Media Outlook 2022-2026”. However, this rapid growth has occurred in a largely unregulated environment, giving rise to multiple ethical issues and harms. As the reliance on personal data intensifies, major tech companies are at the forefront, shaping user experiences and privacy norms. Thus, rapid expansion

has also introduced complex challenges, particularly concerning privacy, ethical advertising practices, and the protection of vulnerable populations.

The Digital Economy Report 2021 points to the complexities involved in governing data and data flows across borders. Digital advertising has a unique feature- precise targeted marketing, providing a surgical accuracy in its reach, slicing and dicing as per desired demography and location, it enables real-time performance analysis. As the industry continues to evolve fueled by advancements in technology and data analytics, there is an increasing urgency to address these issues through robust legal frameworks. The current regulatory landscape is patchy, reflecting starkly different approaches adopted by different countries, with strong influences from the major economic powers. An international framework is urgently needed to address this situation.

The increased interconnection and interdependence challenges in the global data economy call for moving towards a holistic, coordinated global approach. In this regard, International Organizations constantly develop recommendations, guidelines and toolkits. Formalizing such norms through multistakeholder consultations can balance innovation with public welfare. They propose a foundation for harmonizing the growing diversity of laws like GDPR and COPPA through a shared global playbook attuned to the impacts of advertising technologies across human rights and sustainable development goals. Here is the list of international organizations that play a crucial role in consumer protection and advertising regulation in the digital space:

- Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD): The OECD provides a forum for governments to discuss and coordinate policies related to economic and social issues. The OECD addresses digital consumer protection and advertising regulation by developing guidelines and recommendations. They work on issues such as online privacy and cross border flows of personal data, digital security, and consumer rights in the digital age.
- International Telecommunication Union (ITU): ITU is a specialized United Nations agency focusing on information and communication technologies (ICTs). ITU works on global standards and policies related to ICTs. In the context of consumer protection and advertising, it addresses issues like online privacy, cybersecurity, and digital accessibility.
- European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA): ENISA works to improve cybersecurity across the European Union. ENISA plays a role in enhancing consumer protection in the digital space by providing guidelines and

recommendations on cybersecurity best practices. This includes measures to protect consumers from online threats.

- International Chamber of Commerce (ICC): The ICC is the world's largest business organization, representing a global network of businesses. ICC provides guidelines and codes of conduct for responsible advertising and marketing practices. They contribute to shaping ethical standards for digital advertising to ensure fair and transparent practices.
- Internet Advertising Bureau (IAB): IAB is an industry association that focuses on the online advertising industry. IAB develops standards and guidelines for online advertising to ensure transparency, privacy, and responsible practices. This contributes to consumer protection in the digital advertising space.
- International Consumer Protection and Enforcement Network (ICPEN): ICPEN is a network of consumer protection authorities from various countries, working together to address cross-border consumer protection issues. ICPEN provides a platform for member countries to collaborate on tackling online scams, fraud, and deceptive practices. They share information and best practices to enhance consumer protection in the digital realm.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) also the leading UN agency for the promotion and protection of freedom of expression and to information. It contributes to peace and security by promoting international cooperation in education, sciences, culture, communication and information.
- World Health Organization (WHO): While primarily focused on health, WHO also plays a role in regulating digital advertising related to health products and services. WHO provides guidelines for digital advertising in the healthcare sector to ensure that consumers receive accurate and reliable information.

Moreover, International forums like WIPO, OECD, UNCTAD, UNCITRAL, ISO, WTO, Hague Conference on Private International laws, etc., are constantly monitoring upon the formation of International rules which focuses on online advertising and other E-Commerce related issues. Globally harmonized principles and protections surrounding advertising systems are developed in consultation with multiple stakeholders and representatives of countries at dedicated Conferences and Forums. Recommendations in the documents listed below establish the core characteristics for protection of online consumers and effective functioning of E-Commerce:

- OECD Good Practice Guide on Online Advertising 2019. Protecting Consumers in e-commerce
- OECD Toolkit for protecting digital consumers 2018
- Report on the Implementation of the OECD Recommendation on Consumer Protection in E-commerce 2022
- Consumer Protection Legislation Worldwide- UNCTAD Global Cyberlaw Tracker.
- Fresh joint report in 2023 done by UN, World Bank, IMF, OECD, WTO-Digital Trade for Development
- The UN Report on Disinformation: a role for privacy 2021
- United Nations Conference on Trade and Development-UNCTAD Digital Economy Report 2021.
- Legal changes and trends in advertising industry- Global Advertising Lawyers Alliance
- UNESCO Guidelines for the Governance of Digital Platforms 2023
- UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence 2021
- Meta advertising policy principles

As UN Secretary General said, to support safe and equitable digital transformations we need stronger international cooperation to address the challenges that we face, to shape innovation in ways that reflect universal human values. The Summit of the Future in 2024 is an opportunity to agree on multilateral solutions for a better tomorrow, strengthening global governance for both present and future generations. Summit will be held in September 2024, in New York, preceded by a preparatory ministerial meeting to be held a week before. The Summit will adopt a concise, action-oriented outcome document entitled “A Pact for the Future”, agreed in advance by consensus through intergovernmental negotiations. UN brief published in May 2023 proposes the development of a Global Digital Compact that would set out principles, objectives and actions for advancing an open, free, secure and human-centered digital future, anchored in universal human rights, to shape a shared vision on digital cooperation by providing an inclusive global framework to achieve the governance required for a sustainable digital future.

The UN’s convening power offers singular capacities to drive consensus among diverse stakeholders. United Nations can formally propose conventions codifying baseline duties and cooperative oversight mechanisms given the borderless nature of platforms. In 2023 UNESCO, the leading UN agency for the promotion and protection of freedom of expression and to information

published Guidelines for the Governance of Digital Platforms. These Guidelines aim to safeguard the right to freedom of expression and access to information in the context of the governance of digital platforms. Developed through a global-scale multi-stakeholder consultation that gathered more than 10,000 comments from 134 countries, The Internet for Trust conference, organized by UNESCO in February 2023, alone brought together over 4,000 stakeholders from 134 countries. They present a multistakeholder approach outlining key responsibilities for States and digital platforms to fulfill their human rights obligations and define roles for intergovernmental organizations, civil society, media, academia, the technical community, and other stakeholders. These guidelines propose fair, clear, and shared measures: online moderators in all languages, including indigenous ones; greater transparency of platforms and their financing, with better risk assessment; the establishment of independent regulators; the promotion of critical thinking; support for gender equality; and, above all, the safeguarding and strengthening of freedom of expression, cultural diversity, and other human rights.

Also recently, UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence adopted in 2021 by 193 Member States, established a humanist framework for the evolution of this technology. What makes the Recommendation exceptionally applicable are its extensive Policy Action Areas, which allow policymakers to translate the core values and principles into action with respect to data governance among many other spheres. Realizing that digital future requires active guidance by international organizations in establishing multilateral legal frameworks for governing online advertising and allied harms like misinformation, I would also propose forming model of international regulation of Digital Commercial Ethics.

Cultivating an Internet of Trust is a shared responsibility among all stakeholders. It calls upon us all to sustain an enabling environment for freedom of expression and the right to information. We need to avoid the fragmentation of regulations or approaches that compromise human rights and develop consistent responses to virtual spaces with algorithms designed to monopolize our attention, by prioritizing clicks over certainty. Achieving legal upgrades and harmonization of legislation related to digital advertising with international standards requires a coordinated and comprehensive approach.

Practical solutions that could be implemented to address this urgent need should start from: 1) standardization of definitions and terminology, glossary related to digital advertising across jurisdictions to ensure a common

understanding; 2) Encourage countries to adopt and implement international guidelines and best practices, to create a consistent and globally recognized set of standards; 3) Strengthen cooperation among law enforcement agencies across borders to address issues of cross-border advertising violations, facilitate information sharing and collaboration on investigations and legal actions; 4) Ensure that digital advertising legislation incorporates robust data protection and privacy standards. Promote transparency and user consent mechanisms in digital advertising practices. 5) Establish mechanisms for periodic reviews and updates to legislation to keep pace with technological advancements and emerging trends; 6) Encourage the development of industry-wide ethical standards for digital advertising through self-regulation initiatives; 7) Invest in digital literacy programs and consumer education to empower individuals to make informed decisions about digital advertising. Educate consumers on recognizing and reporting deceptive or misleading digital advertising practices; 8) Conduct regular impact assessments of digital advertising legislation to evaluate its effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. Utilize feedback from industry stakeholders, consumers, and experts to refine and enhance legislation; 9) Facilitate international collaboration at forums where countries can share experiences, challenges, and solutions related to digital advertising legislation. Promote ongoing dialogue to foster a shared understanding of the evolving landscape; 10) Establish an intergovernmental organization dedicated to digital commercial ethics standard-setting. An intergovernmental group of experts on consumer protection law and policy, operating within the framework of an existing commission of the Trade and Development Board of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, can provide this institutional support.

Overall, pluralistic pressures spanning binding accords, voluntary self-regulation guided by international standards and consistent scrutiny by principled social actors together can steer tech ecosystems towards equitable innovation centered on human rights.

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